

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF ENSURING QUALITY IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

The quality factor in education is not limited only to the transfer and assimilation of knowledge, but is also considered as a multidimensional and dynamic system aimed at ensuring the intellectual, moral, social and professional development of a person and forming a personality in accordance with the requirements of society. The serious consideration of this factor in our country in recent years gives grounds to say that the issue is urgent. In this regard, in accordance with the goal set, the main directions and modern approaches to ensuring quality in education are analyzed in the scientific and pedagogical level. The process of modernization of education is shown to develop as a complex and integrated structure, linked to reforms, new content and teaching methods, monitoring and evaluation systems. The socio-cultural nature of education is explained in the context of its interaction with personality and culture. The scientific work shows that ensuring quality in education is directly related to the development of human capital, adaptation to new requirements of society formed on the basis of information and technology, integration into international standards and national strategies. Factors such as globalization, information economy and the Bologna process make the assessment and adaptation of education to international standards relevant. In addition, it also examines pedagogical, technological and humanistic factors affecting the quality of education. The article presents the principle of "accessibility-quality-efficiency", considered important for the 21st century, functional literacy, a humanistic education model and the formation of a creative, free and cultural personality as the main goals. The steps taken within the framework of the Education Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan to improve the quality of education, participation in international research and mechanisms for assessing education are particularly emphasized. As a result of the conducted analyses, it is concluded that ensuring quality in education requires a strategic, sustainable and flexible approach not only to the transfer of knowledge, but also to the development of personality, instilling social values and the integration of future generations.

Keywords: Quality of education, modernization of education, socio-cultural approach, modern educational technologies, assessment and monitoring.

Introduction

In the modern era, the quality of education is considered one of the main driving forces of the socio-economic, technological and cultural development of society. Globalization, the rapid development of information technologies and the changing labor market have necessitated the formation of new approaches to the structure, content and function of education [1, p. 43-47]

Ensuring quality in education is a complex process that combines many aspects, and the effectiveness of this process primarily depends on the correct determination of the strategic priorities of the national education policy, teacher training and professionalism, modernization of teaching technologies, and adaptation of the content and methodology of teaching to the challenges of the time. In addition, mechanisms for assessing the results of education, effective organization of monitoring systems, as well as the establishment of national assessment systems integrated with international experience are the main components of this process.

The Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Education" defines the problems of forming a creative personality and citizen. The law states that the main goal of education is to educate independent, creatively thinking citizens and individuals who understand their responsibility to the Azerbaijani state, respect the national traditions and principles of democracy, human

rights and freedoms of their people, are loyal to the ideas of patriotism and Azerbaijaniness [2, p. 4]. The expected result of the implementation of this main goal is the upbringing of active Azerbaijani citizens.

The large-scale reforms carried out in the field of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan in recent years and the adopted "State Strategy for the Development of Education" have defined specific goals and directions of action in this direction. The strategic approach of the state to achieving quality in education has brought to the agenda such main tasks as increasing the functional literacy of students and equipping them with knowledge and skills that meet the requirements of the labor market.

In this regard, the presented scientific article analyzes in detail the theoretical and practical aspects of the concept of quality in education, internal and external factors influencing the formation of this quality, priority directions of education policy, and issues such as harmonization of the education system with international indicators. The goal is to reveal the methodological foundations of ensuring quality in education, identify existing problems, and put forward effective proposals in this direction.

1. The quality factor in education and its socio-cultural significance

Many countries of the world, as well as many higher education institutions, struggle with widespread

low-quality education due to the lack of effective strategies to improve the quality of their education systems.

The term quality assurance refers to “systematic, structured and continuous attention to quality in terms of maintaining and improving quality”.

In a broad sense, quality assurance is defined as systematic planning, monitoring and evaluation to maintain and improve the standards of education, research and general services in colleges and universities in order to ensure effective results. That is, it is understood as the ability of higher education institutions to meet certain criteria related to academic matters, staff-student ratio, staff structure by position, staff development, material and technical base, financing opportunities, compliance with high standards in management and evaluation of their results[3; 4]

Modernization of education is an objective process that determines its reform and progress towards the formation of new meanings and values, approaches to the content and teaching methods of education, monitoring and evaluation of the results of educational activities. The modernization program for the development of the country is based on the principle of development of the education system, and therefore education should be mainly modern, advanced, supporting objective social development trends, and be all-encompassing. The formation of state education policy of the XXI century. in this case, they are based on the slogan “accessibility - quality - efficiency”. It is an integrated system that synthesizes all stages of education, which is the basis of a social indicator of the quality of education. Preservation and provision of the quality of education is a very big responsibility that requires a strong sense of responsibility. This issue is of concern all over the world, as each country strives to provide high-quality education [5, p. 767].

In the sociocultural approach, society, education, which is a cultural phenomenon, and personality act as sociocultural systems that interact with each other. Culture determines not only the external environment of education, but also its “internal world”, its structure. It is no coincidence that researchers have recently been using the concept of “cultural-educational space”, thereby considering education as a spiritual and cultural process. In this sense, revealing the relationship between education and culture, their mutual relations and mutual influences, in other words, clarifying the concept of “education” and the place of culture in it, and vice versa, clarifying the concept of “culture” and the place of education in it, is one of the urgent issues [6, p. 99].

The quality of education is an assessment of the integrity of the content of education, teaching technologies, monitoring methods and the subject's self-determination in terms of individual development and the requirements of society in new socio-economic conditions. In this regard, the quality of education is perceived as a concept, reflecting the ability to ensure the achievement of the goals set for the education system, to ensure its compliance with the needs of a particular person in education, the needs of society and the economy. The exceptional importance of ensuring the

quality of education today is determined by the following objective reasons:

Firstly, scientific and technological progress is accelerating and the dependence of the level and scale of education on the development of society is increasing. In such conditions, higher education is becoming widespread and it is necessary to create conditions for the development of the creative abilities of those entering higher educational institutions, and vocational education is being made available to the general population.

Secondly, there is a gradual transition of society from the industrial stage of the economy to the information economy and the stage of the formation of an information civilization. This process is mainly associated with an increase in the economic and social role of universities and their graduates.

Thirdly, with the development of world information civilization, the process of globalization is developing rapidly, part of which is the accumulation of scientific information in accordance with the Bologna process, which is associated with the provision of an international education, which requires the harmonization of the level of work quality of educational systems of different countries, the compliance of young people with certain universal criteria and standards, in particular, the international mobility of graduates and students, their employment and the recognition of educational certificates.

Fourthly, taking into account the rapid development of Azerbaijan in the field of education, the issue of taking its material and technical base among the technologically, economically and culturally developed countries of the world is sharply reflected.

For these and many other reasons, the quality of education takes one of the most important places in the system of economic and socio-political development of our country, and we are witnessing its transition to a new quality level. In general, a change in the paradigm of training students and specialists, reflecting the educational priorities and requirements of society, different content, different approaches to learning, different attitudes, behavior and a different pedagogical idea, is manifested. In modern conditions, school teachers are faced with an individual training that knows how to deal with the environment. The level of culture and education is the basis of the quality indicators of education in the 21st century, the formation of a personality that meets the requirements of the humanistic and information society in modern living conditions.

The quality of education determines the "quality of life of a person and society", since it is also determined by the personal, ideological, civic development of the younger generation and the orientation of its emotional value to the world around it. Thus, the problem of the quality of education should be considered, first of all, from the point of view of the human and social value of education. Because a full-fledged education received by a person not only gives him certain knowledge about nature, man, society, but also allows him to know himself and subsequently show himself as a citizen.

The scientific humanistic education system can achieve three main goals: the formation of a cultural

person (cultural subject), a free citizen (historical subject, civil society), a creative person (subject of activity, self-development).

The implementation of this goal is aimed at solving the following tasks:

- Education of a person with his own abilities and needs in the main forms of human activity;
- Development of the ability to recognize himself in unity with the world, in dialogue with it;
- Development of the ability to self-determination, self-expression based on the restoration and assimilation of the cultural experience of humanity's self-development;
- Formation of the need and ability to communicate with the world on the basis of humanistic values and ideals, the rights of a free person.

Today, the process of reforming the education system is actively developing, accompanied by the widespread use of effective mechanisms for implementing educational goals and the application of scientific methods for assessing educational achievements.

The next important task in ensuring the quality of education is the development and transformation of various educational technologies for teachers. The quality of education depends on how and what technologies the teacher relies on, how he can change his methodological tools depending on the characteristics of the students.

Humanity has truly entered a new historical space, when the person himself, his educational and professional skills, moral qualities have become the main source of development. The vital activity of mankind is directed towards very complex objects and is characterized by high technology.

2. Quality education: basic concepts and definitions

The most important aspect of the educational process is its quality. The quality of education is the ability of educational workers to meet the needs and requirements of society at the expected level with their knowledge, skills and behavior [7, p. 40]. Is it possible to produce quality services and quality products with a workforce that is not well educated and does not have a qualified profession? In which factory can quality products be produced with unqualified technical staff? What quality health care can be provided with a medical staff that is not well educated? There are many similar examples. For this reason, the whole world is trying to achieve quality in education today. Because the nation that has the best quality in education obtains quality products and services produced by quality professionals and qualified specialists [8, p. 16].

One of the main factors for achieving successful and quality education is the teacher. Training qualified teachers is one of the important tasks facing countries that want to achieve quality. Quality, efficiency and effectiveness in education are based on a professional teaching staff, and professional professional quality in teaching is based on a teacher training model based on scientific principles [9, p. 21-28].

Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Education" defines the quality levels of education as follows:

– The quality level of education is determined in accordance with the principles of the international and pan-European education system on the basis of the state educational and professional standards adopted in the country and in accordance with the relevant quality indicators system for educational levels (educational programs, level of preparation of applicants, material and technical base, infrastructure, information resources, professionalism and scientific and pedagogical level of educators, progressive teaching technologies, etc.).

– The quality level of personnel training in an educational institution is determined by the competitiveness of graduates in the national and international labor market, their role in the social and economic development of the country.

– The quality level of education arises from the requirements related to socio-political, socio-economic, scientific and cultural development at each historical stage and is assessed accordingly by the accreditation service [2, p. 5].

In this regard, the concept of "quality of education" has acquired international citizenship, and improving the quality of education has become one of the main tasks of long-term prospective educational institutions. With the change in the level of development of society and social conditions, new requirements are imposed on the quality of education, especially related to the ethical component of a person's creative and predictive abilities. Taking into account the constant variability of the social environment, the concept of "quality of education" will constantly change in the future.

The concept of "quality of education" based on the legislation of our republic in the field of education is interpreted as a certain level of knowledge and skills acquired by graduates of an educational institution in accordance with the planned goals of teaching and education.

The quality of education is the ratio of the goal and the result, the system of actions that are projected to achieve the goals set for operational activity and the zone of potential development of students. The quality of education allows us to consider it not only as a result, but also as a complex dynamic process of development due to changes in the activities of educational institutions and individuals and changes in the surrounding social, economic, technological and political environment [10].

The integration of skills and knowledge, their transfer, interpenetration, and synthesis, in general, implies a high level of education; it allows us to realize the need for self-affirmation, self-expression, self-development, self-determination, and, as a result, is a criterion for the development and social readiness of the individual. A competent person in a particular field has general knowledge and relevant abilities that allow him to justify this field and effectively act in this field. This is a personality that reflects the ability to use knowledge and skills universally and allows him to make decisions and act in non-standard situations (synergistic approach) on the subject.

Thus, the quality of education is not only the results of work, but also a system, model, and organization that ensures the comprehensive personal and social development of students.

In this regard, the quality of education reflects the following complex indicators:

- Correction of goals and learning outcomes;
- Ensuring the degree of dependence of the expectations of participants in the educational process on the provided educational service;
- A certain level of knowledge, skills, abilities, abilities and competencies of the individual, mental, physical and moral development;

From the point of view of modern didactics, the following features of the quality of education are taken into account:

1. The conceptual level of content corresponding to the level of scientific and technical progress;
2. Interdisciplinary, the nature of knowledge, skills and activities;
3. Adaptation to the interests, desires, capabilities and individual characteristics of students;
4. The variable, alternative and problematic nature of training with the widespread use of information technologies;
5. The creation of diverse cultural environments for multicultural education in order to enrich themselves and ensure readiness to live in a multinational environment;
6. The independent nature of the assessment of educational outcomes and the level of personality development;
7. Providing conditions for self-assessment, self-certification and self-management in learning and development.

The result of quality education is the formation of such abilities (characteristics) of individuals: self-organization, including spiritual; self-transformation activities; self-expression. Finally, a well-educated person must be competitive, successful and in demand in the labor market. It is necessary to easily and freely adapt to rapidly changing socio-economic conditions, to use the education received effectively. Each person must manage the four main stages of education: acquiring knowledge, learning to work, learning to develop personality, learning to live. This integrated approach to education has caused discussions in a number of countries around the world and has had a significant impact on the training of teacher cadres and the development of teaching [11, pp. 25-28].

3. Pedagogical principles of quality education

Recently, the growing demands on the quality of educational services have become increasingly noticeable, allowing the formation of the following pedagogical principles of quality education:

- A competency-based approach to the educational needs of students and their profiles, focusing educational programs and educational technologies on the personality and developmental characteristics;
- Consistency, integrity and variability of the content and activities of education, taking into account multiple points of view of the problem and multiple directions of its solution;

- The transition to the relations of mutual activity of educational subjects in the educational process;
- Activity as a subject of education and creative activity of students in the field of self-development, self-determination;
- The modular-block principle of organizing the content of education and the activities of students;
- Principles of progress in learning and development, support for motivation, self-assessment, self-management and self-correction;
- To be oriented towards the future content of life and activity, humanistic values and ideals; to approach learning and studying in the future not as a school of memory, but as a school of thought; to form a person who creates an image in the world through active self-reliance in the world of objective, social and spiritual culture.

In the document "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated October 24, 2013, the quality of education was declared the main strategic priority, and the improvement of the quality indicators of students and graduates of general education institutions was put forward as a pressing issue [12].

A distinctive feature of the development of education in the world today is the increased attention of the governments of developed countries to the problems of the quality and efficiency of education. Education is becoming a strategic area that ensures national security, and the competitiveness of the country is assessed by the level of education of the younger generation. Many countries are joining forces in the development of methodology, technology and tools for comparative studies of the quality of education. At the same time, the direction of explaining the differences between countries in terms of the level of material preparation of students, and in particular, identifying the factors affecting the results that determine the highest achievements, is also in the spotlight.

The State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan states that "Quality and inclusiveness of education. According to the United Nations Human Development Report for 2010, compared to 2005, Azerbaijan has advanced 34 steps, rising from 101st to 67th place among 169 countries, and has entered the "medium human development" group into the "high human development" group. Azerbaijan has achieved great achievements in terms of reducing poverty and increasing life expectancy by accelerating the pace of economic development. At the same time, statistical analyses of leading international organizations show that it is necessary to increase the international competitiveness indicators of Azerbaijani education and the rating level of higher education institutions located in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan" [12].

The creation of a system for assessing the quality of education in Azerbaijan is associated with the need to obtain objective information on learning outcomes in accordance with educational standards in order to make sound management decisions. This requires criteria for

comparing the reliability of the assessment system. One of these principles is the use of advanced management systems from the experience of foreign countries, which allow us to identify trends in the development of systems for assessing learning outcomes in different countries of the world, and systems for assessing the results of research in schools used in different countries of the world.

In accordance with the relevant Decree signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on 29.12.2019, the Accreditation and Nostrification Department of the Ministry of Education (currently the Ministry of Science and Education) was reorganized by transforming it into the Agency for Quality Assurance in Education with the status of a public legal entity under the Ministry of Education. The Agency is responsible for the assessment of higher, secondary and additional education based on standards accepted in Azerbaijan and internationally. It is a professional and expert institution in the field of independent assessment of the quality of education.

The Agency for Quality Assurance in Education (AKEA) ensures the definition of quality levels of educational programs and the implementation of requirements. While fulfilling its duties and exercising its rights, the Agency interacts with state bodies (institutions) and municipalities, international and non-governmental organizations, other legal entities and individuals [13].

Proceeding from this, in recent years, Azerbaijan has participated in international studies of educational achievements. International studies on the assessment of the quality of education allow assessing the state of the education system in Azerbaijan and in the international context using the same pedagogical measurement tools created taking into account international priorities in education.

Along with this, special attention should be paid to determining the interdisciplinary knowledge of students, especially the use of information to solve practical problems, and it should be characterized as follows.

- Assessing the functional literacy of students in order to determine their ability to adapt to modern society;
- Determining the educational achievements of students in terms of modern international priorities in the field of improving the quality of education;
- To determine the direction of education development, analyze the achievements in the field of education, identify its strengths and weaknesses, etc. The pedagogical characteristics of the quality of modern education, the development of young people's skills, the principles of its provision and assessment constitute the requirements for new educational standards, which should determine the requirements for the quality of students' educational achievements, which consists of the development of teaching and learning technologies, control methods and assessment of the quality of education.

4. Conceptual aspects of quality assurance in education

Conceptual aspects of quality assurance in education are mainly related to the creation of learning conditions:

- Educational policy for quality improvement;
- Clearly and unambiguously defined criteria, rules, quality standards of educational content;
- The quality of curricula and didactic materials for teachers and students, the quality level of material, social, household and information infrastructure of educational institutions;
- Means of influencing the subjects of the educational process, including special technologies for organizing educational and teaching processes, methods for assessing the quality of education;
- Using modern tools and technologies for objective quality control of education;
- Informatization of education (professional databases, electronic textbooks and libraries, daily use of telecommunication services in the classroom and independent academic work);
- Mechanisms and tools for managing educational activities in terms of quality and self-management.

Thus, the quality of education largely depends on the quality of the components of the management system of the entire education system and its subjects. Such an important category as the quality of education forces us to study the phenomenon of a new management culture that must be mastered by management, teachers and students. The problem of achieving quality is associated with an understanding of the objective function of education and a systematic approach to education at each level, considered as an activity to achieve the goals of the organization and coordinating the activities of all components of the education system.

Conclusion

Ensuring quality in education in the modern era is a complex and strategic process that is closely related not only to the improvement of pedagogical and didactic approaches, but also to social, economic, technological and cultural factors. From this perspective, the quality of education is determined not only by the academic performance of students, but also by their personal and civic formation, the development of functional literacy, the ability to communicate with the environment and their readiness for future professional activity. The main indicators that ensure the quality of education - accessibility, efficiency, technological integration, teacher training, updating of teaching technologies and the objectivity of assessment systems - shape the direction of reforms in this area.

The educational reforms carried out in the Republic of Azerbaijan in recent years, especially the targeted steps aimed at increasing quality within the framework of the "State Strategy for the Development of Education", have created an opportunity to renew the education system in terms of structure and content, and to bring it into line with international indicators. At the same time, within the framework of the Bologna process, the international competitiveness of education, the flexibility of graduates in the labor market and the global mobility of students have become key priorities.

The experience gained shows that one of the main conditions for improving the quality of education is the improvement of the professionalism of teachers, the application of modern teaching methods and the systematic integration of approaches aimed at the individual development of students into teaching. At the same time, the establishment of objective, transparent and analytical systems based on international criteria in the assessment of educational outcomes is of great importance in terms of reflecting the real state of education and determining development directions.

Thus, ensuring quality in education is not only a goal, but also a fundamental means of ensuring the sustainable development of an entire society. In this direction, strategic thinking, effective management, scientifically based pedagogical decisions and investments in human capital are the main guarantees of long-term social well-being and national competitiveness.

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